

Research

Modeling and MATLAB based Simulation of an 8-DoF Light-Weight Humanoid Manipulator

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Abstract: This article picks an 8-DoF, Light-Weight, flexible, and cost-effective Humanoid Robotic Manipulator as a Research topic and focuses on its design, implementation, control, and simulation. The primary task is to design the basic model by designing software. By keeping the degrees of freedom in mind, a simulation platform is selected to carry out the test of the model. For this purpose, the MATLAB and Simulink are opted to perform the simulations of the assigned tasks. After being comfortable with design and simulation platforms, the next step was to analyze the Kinematics of the Manipulator. So, for the kinematics computation, D-H Parameters are defined for forward and reverse kinematics. Finally, a series of experimental scenes such as Grasping ball and imitating action is intended to extensively examine the stability, accuracy, speed, and flexible movement of humanoid robotic manipulator LWH-Arm.

Keywords: Humanoid Robotic Arm, manipulator, 8-DoF, Light-Weight.

I. Introduction

Robotics is a widely studied field that has extended for many decades. One of the studies within the robotics research community is humanoid robotics. The objective of humanoid robotics is to develop human-like manipulator which resembles human arms characteristics and can assist human in daily life. The design and control method exists varying performances related to flexibility, precision, speed, and cost.

There are different types of robotic manipulators such as Linear robots, Cylindrical robots, Spherical/Polar robots, SCARA Robot, etc. The main action in a humanoid robot comes from the

arm of the manipulator, arm has the advantage of small size, lightweight, lifting capability, flexibility, and smooth movement. Furthermore, its hardware (design), software, control algorithms, and experimental environment are challenging in the field of humanoid robotics. The main difficulty is in the development process that how to comprehensively utilize the knowledge of mechanical design, control method, artificial intelligence, and machine learning, to design, assemble, joint, and control the humanoid manipulator.

This article focuses on the design, simulation, control, and lightweight humanoid robotic manipulator. The development process of humanoid robots includes mechanical design, electronics, modeling, computational simulation, control method, evaluation, and improvement. If the robotic manipulator is self-designed and developed it will be cost-effective, as the parts required to purchase motor, materials, etc. are not expensive. Therefore, in this article, we design a robotic arm similar in shape and size to a human arm, then study the control of a simulated manipulator. Manipulate the robotic arm through simulation and check the performance by experiments such as grab and stack, pick and place, catch box.

The main contribution of this article is to research and design the light-weighted robotic manipulator which has a characteristic of the human arm while performing the task. We have designed the 3D model of the manipulator in SOLIDWORKS. After the design is finished, we exported it to simulation software (MATLAB). In MATLAB we will check the performance for flexibility, accuracy, etc. After this, we will 3D print and then assemble them together

II. Mechanical Design

➤ Robotic Arm Design

The primary task was to prepare a model for the manipulator and it is similar to a human arm. The Human arm is composed of bones (humerus, radius, ulna), muscles, nerve supply, blood supply, and veins. Bones and muscles are connected together to form an arm. Mimicking human arm anatomy, size, and characteristics we have designed our robotic arm. Which is connected to each other by joints and links. Studying, designing, modeling, and assembling the LWH-Arm 0.4 and LWH-Arm 0.5 structure and characteristics in front. We have designed LWH-Arm 1.0.

LWH-Arm0.4 is based on ODE physics engine calculation. Features of this platform include: shape design, mass distribution, kinematics, and inverse kinematics calculations, etc. whereas, LWH-Arm 0.5 designs have given us the huge benefit to design LWH-Arm 1.0. LWH-Arm 1.0.

Fig.1 LWH-Arm 0.4, LWH-Arm 0.5, LWH-Arm 1.0

➤ **Base Stand**

The base is designed to support the structure of the robotic manipulator, so that arm can perform any task without affecting its capability. The base will help the robotic manipulator in smooth movement and accuracy.

Fig.2 Manipulator Stand

➤ **Shoulder**

The shoulder will be attached to the base using nuts and bolts making sure that they are tight enough so that the robotic manipulator can perform without affecting its liability.

Fig.3 Shoulder with parts, Shoulder

➤ **Upper Arm**

The upper arm is connected with shoulder by servo connector and shoulder connector using nuts and bolts. The upper arm is made up of four parts upper arm 1, upper arm 2, bearing, and standard servo motor. While designing the upper arm we had a tone of ideas but not all of them were fruitful. LWH-Arm 0.4 (arm was vibrating) and LWH-Arm 0.5 (less shuddering but still not steady) provide assistance to modification.

Fig.4 Upper Arm with parts

➤ **Lower Arm with Elbow**

The lower arm is one of the very important part while designing because if its structure is not rigid enough which will have a consequence on our end result, either by making vibration or friction. Keeping human arm structure with its characteristic in our mind we have mimicked the lower arm structure while designing.

Fig.5 Lower Arm with parts

➤ **Forearm, Wrist and End Effector**

Forearm, Wrist, and End Effector are also important segments. Their design without proper research is a very difficult task. LWH-Arm 0.4 and LWH-Arm 0.5 have provided a heap of knowledge which was helpful in designing these parts.

Fig.6 Forearm, Wrist and End Effector

➤ **A Light-Weight Robotic Manipulator**

All parts like a base stand, shoulder, upper arm, lower arm, forearm, wrist, and end effector were designed separately and then linked together using mate function to make robotic manipulator.

Fig.7 Front and 3D view of Manipulator

III. Kinematics of a Manipulator

In robotics, kinematics is used to describe the motion of the systems composed of joined parts (multi-link system) such as robotic manipulators. It illustrates the relationship between the linkage of the robot with the position, orientation, and acceleration.

Fig.8 Forward and Inverse Kinematics

➤ **DH Parameters**

Jacques Denavit and Richard S. Hartenberg introduced first this method, which is used for selecting a frame of reference for the robotic manipulator. In the convention, a coordinate frame is attached to the joints between two links to describe the location of each link relative to its previous one.

Fig.9 Links, Joints and initial position of Manipulator

There are four parameters used in DH parameter representation. θ_i indicates the angle variable of joint i , d_i indicates the line offset distance of each joint axis, a_i indicates offset distance of link i , α_i indicates axis angle between joint i and joint $i - 1$.

Table 1. D-H Parameters

Joint	$\theta_i(variable)$	$d_i(m)$	$a_i(m)$	$\alpha_i(rad)$
Shoulder	θ_1	L1	0	$\pi/2$
Upper Arm	θ_2	0	0	0
Lower Arm	θ_3	0	L2	0
Elbow	θ_4	0	L3	0
Forearm	θ_5	0	0	$-\pi/2$
Upper wrist	θ_6	0	0	$\pi/2$
Lower wrist	θ_7	L4	0	$\pi/2$

IV. Simulation

➤ **Simulation Platform**

Simulink is a graphical programming environment in MATLAB for modeling, simulating, and analyzing multidomain dynamical system.

Fig.10 Front and 3D view of Manipulator

➤ **Control Algorithm**

Simulink is used while designing the controller for the manipulator. The controller is built to illustrate the movement of the robot within the workspace. It adopts that the robotic manipulator is picking up three objects and put them on target.

Fig.11 Flow Chart

V. Experiment and Results

In MATLAB we have imported the SOLIDWORKS model and design control system in it with the help of Simulink. The environment is created and the motor is controlled in PD mode. Following is the experiment that is performed

➤ Grasping Ball

In this experiment we have used an end effector for grasping the ball and move it to the hallowed box. When the target place is reached the end effector/gripper will release the ball into the hallowed box. Fig. 13 shows the joint position while simulation.

Fig.12 Grasping ball Experiment

Fig.13 Joint position

➤ **Imitating Grasping**

In this experiment, we have set the scene the same as the previous one. The simulation represents a control algorithm of the manipulator imitating for picking 3 objects from the table, the object can be of any shape. In Imitating grasping action first manipulator will reach from the rest position to the front desk and will mimic the actions that the gripper is grasping object. Once the gripper is closed then it will move to the right side to place the object in its target position. After that, the gripper will return to the front desk and pick the object and again will place it on the right side of the table. After the second object is to place the manipulator will return back to the front desk for grasping the object which will be placed on the left side of the table after placing it will return to the front desk where simulation will be end. In the following figures we can see the simulation and the joint positions.

Fig.14 Imitating and Joint position

VI. Conclusion

This point of interest for research in this article was an 8-DoF, Light-Weight, flexible, and cost-effective Humanoid Robotic Manipulator. The main focus of this study was to design, implement, control, and simulate the model. The primary task was to design the basic model by designing software. By keeping the degrees of freedom in mind, a simulation platform was selected to carry out the test of the model. For this purpose, the MATLAB and Simulink were opted to perform the simulations of the assigned tasks. After being comfortable with design and simulation platforms, the next step was to analyze the Kinematics of the Manipulator. So, for the kinematics computation, D-H Parameters were defined for forward and reverse kinematics. Finally, a series of experimental scenes such as Grasping ball and imitating action was carried out to extensively examine the stability, accuracy, speed, and flexible movement of humanoid robotic manipulator LWH-Arm. Our main aim was to create such manipulator which is flexible, rigid, coast effective and which can be used anywhere like for teaching, research purpose, homes, and factory providing assist to all. We used different tools to achieve our target. The research results of this paper provide a practicable solution.

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Dedication

This research study is dedicated to our community. Best wishes to them. We wish them a prosperous future.

Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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